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A Creative Folio

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lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
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ANTONIETA S. PALASAN, Ph.D

Associate Professor V

Mindanao State University - Integrated Laboratory School

Marawi City, Lanao Del Sur, BARMM

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THE VOICE OF MOTHER NATURE

Beauty divine, your wonders unfold,
A living story, timeless and bold.
Your quiet grace, your gentle hue,
We breathe, we live, because of you.

Through rolling fields and mountains high,
Your gifts surround, your blessings lie.
The greens that bloom, the skies that gleam,
You paint our world, a perfect dream.

We hear the trees in soft delight,
Their whispers dance in golden light.
The breeze that cools, the streams that play,
All sing your song both night and day.

O Mother dear, how kind, how pure,
Your love unending shall endure.
But we, your children, blind with greed,
Forget your cry, your silent plea.

Now thunder speaks, the earth will quake,
The seas will roar, the mountains shake.
Your trembling heart, your mournful sound,
Reminds us life is sacred ground.

You breathe, you move, you weep, you call,
Your voice resounds to one and all.
A tale of power, fierce yet true
The soul of Earth still speaks through you.